

ON SOME CHARACTERIZATION OF SMARANDACHE - BOOLEAN NEAR - RING WITH SUB-DIRECT SUM STRUCTURE

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Abstract In this paper, we introduced Samarandache-2-algebraic structure of Boolean-near-ring namely Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring. A Samarandache-2-algebraic structure on a set N means a weak algebraic structure S_1 on N such that there exist a proper subset M of N , which is embedded with a stronger algebraic structure S_2 , stronger algebraic structure means satisfying more axioms, that is $S_1 \ll S_2$, by proper subset one understands a subset different from the empty set, from the unit element if any, from the whole set [3]. We define Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring and obtain the some of its characterization through Boolean-ring with sub-direct sum structure. For basic concept of near-ring we refer to G.Pilz [11].

Keywords Boolean-ring, Boolean-near-ring, Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring, Compatibility, Maximal set, Idempotent and uni-element.

§1. Preliminaries

Definition 1.1. A (Left) near ring A is a system with two Binary operations, addition and multiplication, such that

- (i) the elements of A form a group $(A, +)$ under addition,
- (ii) the elements of A form a multiplicative semi-group,
- (iii) $x(y+z) = xy+xz$, for all x, y and $z \in A$.

In particular, if A contains a multiplicative semi-group S whose elements generates $(A, +)$ and satisfy,

- (iv) $(x+y)s = xs+ys$, for all $x,y \in A$ and $s \in S$, then we say that A is a distributively generated near-ring.

Definition 1.2. A near-ring $(B, +, \cdot)$ is Boolean-near-ring if there exists a Boolean-ring $(A, +, \wedge, 1)$ with identity such that \cdot is defined in terms of $+$, \wedge and 1 , and for any $b \in B$, $b \cdot b = b$.

Definition 1.3. A near-ring $(B, +, \cdot)$ is said to be idempotent if $x^2 = x$, for all $x \in B$.

- (ie) If $(B, +, \cdot)$ is an idempotent ring, then for all $a, b \in B$, $a + a = 0$ and $a \cdot b = b \cdot a$

Definition 1.4. Compatibility $a \in b$ (ie) "a is compatibility to b") if $ab^2 = a^2b$.

Definition 1.5. Let $A = (\dots, a, b, c, \dots)$ be a set of pairwise compatible elements of an associate ring R . Let A be maximal in the sense that each element of A is compatible with

every other element of A and no other such elements may be found in R . Then A is said to be a maximal compatible set or a maximal set.

Definition 1.6. If a sub-direct sum R of domains has an identity, and if R has the property that with each element a , it contains also the associated idempotent a^0 of a , then R is called an associate subdirect sum or an associate ring.

Definition 1.7. If the maximal set A contains an element u which has the property that $a < u$, for all $a \in A$, then u is called the uni-element of A .

Definition 1.8. Left zero divisors are right zero divisors, if $ab=0$ implies $ba=0$.

Now we have introduced a new definition by[3]

Definition 1.9. A Boolean- near- ring B is said to be Samarandache- Boolean- near- ring whose proper subset A is a Boolean- ring with respect to same induced operation of B .

Theorem 1.1. A Boolean-near-ring (B, \vee, \wedge) is having the proper subset A , is a maximal set with uni-element in an associate ring R , with identity under suitable definitions for $(B, +, \cdot)$ with corresponding lattices (A, \leq) $(A, <)$ and

$$a \vee b = a + b - 2a^0b = (a \cup b) - (a \cap b)$$

$$a \wedge b = a \cap b = a^0b = ab^0.$$

Then B is a Samarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Proof. Given (B, \vee, \wedge) is a Boolean-near- ring whose proper subset (A, \vee, \wedge) is a maximal set with uni-element in an associate Ring R , and if the maximal set A is also a subset of B .

Now to prove that B is Samarandache-Boolean-near-ring. It is enough to prove that the proper subset A of B is a Boolean-ring. Let a and b be two constants of A : If a is compatible to b , we define $a \wedge b$ as follows :

If $a_i = b_i$ in the i -component, let $(a \wedge b)_i = 0_i$

If $a_i \neq b_i$, then since $a \sim b$ precisely one of these is zero.

If $a_i = 0$, let $(a \wedge b)_i = b_i \neq 0$;

If $b_i = 0$, let $(a \wedge b)_i = a_i \neq 0$

It is seen that if $a \wedge b$ belongs to the associate ring R , then $a \wedge b < u$, where u is the uni-element of A , and therefore, $a \wedge b \in A$

$$\text{Consider } a \wedge b = a + b - 2a^0b$$

If in the i -component, $0 \neq a_i - b_i$, then since $(a^0)_i = 1_i = (b^0)_i$,

$$\text{we have } (a + b - 2a^0b)_i = 0_i \text{ and,}$$

If $0_i = a_i = b_i$, then $(a^0)_i = 0$ and $(b^0)_i = 1$, whence,

$$(a + b - 2a^0b)_i = b_i$$

If $a_i \neq 0$ and $b_i = 0$ then $(a + b - 2a^0b) = 0_i$

Therefore $a \wedge b \in A$, the maximal set.

Similarly, the element $a \wedge b = a \cap b = a^0b = ab^0 = \text{glb}(a, b)$ has defined and shown to belong to A as the $\text{glb}(a, b)$ Now let us show that (A, \vee, \wedge) is a Boolean - ring: Firstly, $a \vee a = 0$, since $a_i = a_i$ in every i -component, whence $(a \vee a)_i$ vanishes, by our definition of ' \vee '. Secondly $a \wedge a =$

$a \cap a = a^0 a = a$, and so a is idempotent under \wedge . We shown that A is closed under \wedge is \vee . And associativity is a direct verification, and each element is itself inverse under \wedge .

To prove associativity under \wedge :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } a \wedge (b \wedge c) &= a^0 (b \wedge c) \\ &= a^0 (b^0 c) \\ &= a^0 (bc^0) \\ &= (a^0 b) c^0 \\ &= (a \wedge b)^0 c = (a \wedge b) \wedge c \\ \Rightarrow a \wedge (b \wedge c) &= (a \wedge b) \wedge c, \text{ for all } a, b, c \in R \end{aligned}$$

For distributivity of \wedge over \vee ,

Let c be an arbitrary in A

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } c \wedge (a \vee b) &= c^0 (a \vee b) \\ &= c^0 (a \cup b) - c^0 (a \cap b) \\ &= (c^0 a \cup c^0 b) - c^0 a^0 b \\ &= c^0 a + c^0 b - c^0 a^0 b - c^0 a^0 b \\ &= c^0 a + c^0 b - 2c^0 a^0 b \\ &= (c \wedge a) \vee (c \wedge b) \\ \Rightarrow c \wedge (a \vee b) &= (c \wedge a) \vee (c \wedge b) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(A \vee, \wedge)$ is a Boolean-ring.

\therefore It follows that the proper subset A , a maximal set of B forms a Boolean ring.

$\therefore B$ is a Boolean-near-ring, whose proper subset is a Boolean-ring, Then by definition, B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Theorem 1.2. A Boolean-near-ring (B, \vee, \wedge) is having the proper subset $(A, +, \wedge, 1)$ is an associate ring in which the relation of compatibility is transitive for non-zero elements with identity under suitable definitions for $(B, +, \cdot)$ with corresponding lattices (A, \leq) $(A, <)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} a \vee b &= a + b - 2a^0 b = (a \cup b) - (a \cap b) \\ a \wedge b &= a \cap b = a^0 b = ab^0. \end{aligned}$$

Then B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Proof.

Assume that $(B, +, \cdot)$ be Boolean- near-ring having a proper subset A is an associate ring in which the relation of compatibility is transitive for non-zero elements.

Now to prove that B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

(ie) to prove that if the proper subset of B is a Boolean-ring, then by definition B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring. we have 0 is compatible with all elements, whence all elements are compatible with A and therefore, are idempotent.

Then assume that transitivity holds for compatibility of non-zero elements. It follows that non-zero elements from two maximal sets cannot be compatible (much less equal), and hence, except for the element 0 , the maximal sets are disjoint.

Let a be a arbitrary, non-zero element of R . If a is a zero-divisor of R , then the idempotent element $A - a^0 \neq 0$.

Further $A - a^0$ belongs to the maximal set generated by the non-zero divisor $a' = a + A - a^0$,

since it is $(A-a^0)a' = (A-a^0)(a+A-a^0)$
 $= (A-a^0) = (A-a^0)^2$

(ie) $A-a^0 < a'$. Since also $a < a'$ and $a \sim A - a^0$ Therefore, a is idempotent.

(ie) All the zero-divisors of R are idempotent which is a maximal set then by theorem 1 and by definition A is a Boolean-ring. Then by definition, Therefore B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Theorem 1.3.

A Boolean-near-ring (B, \vee, \wedge) is having the proper subset A , the set A of idempotent elements of a ring R , with suitable definitions for \vee and \wedge ,

$$a \vee b = a + b - 2a^0b = (a \cup b) - (a \cap b)$$

$$a \wedge b = a \cap b = a^0b = ab^0.$$

Then B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Proof.

Assume that the set A of idempotent elements of a ring R , which is also a subset of B . Now to prove that B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring. It is sufficient to prove that the set A of idempotent elements of a ring R with identity forms a maximal set in R with uni-element.

By the definition of compatible, then we have every element of R is compatible with every other idempotent element.

If $a \in R$ is not idempotent then,

$a^2 \cdot 1 \neq a \cdot 1^2$, since the definition of compatible. Hence no non-idempotent can belong to this maximal set. Thus the set A is idempotent element of R with identity forms a maximal set in R whose uni-element is the identity of R , by theorem 1 and by definition. A , a maximal set of B forms a Boolean ring

Then by definition

It conclude that B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Theorem 1.4.

A Boolean-near-ring (B, \vee, \wedge) is having the proper subset, having a non-zero divisor of A , as an associate ring. with suitable definitions for \vee and \wedge ,

$$a \vee b = a + b - 2a^0b = (a \cup b) - (a \cap b)$$

$$a \wedge b = a \cap b = a^0b = ab^0.$$

Then B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Proof.

Let B is Boolean-near-ring whose proper subset having a non-zero divisor of associate ring A .

Now to prove that B Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

It is enough to prove that every non-divisor of A determines uniquely a maximal set of A with uni-element.

Let a be the uni-element of a maximal set A then we have $b < a$, for $b \in A$

Consider all the elements of A in whose sub-direct display one or more component a_i duplicate the corresponding component u_i of u , the other components of a being zeros.

(ie) all the element a such that $a < u$, becomes u is uni-element.

Clearly, these elements are compatible with each other and together with u form a maximal set

in A , for which u is the uni-element.

Hence A is a maximal set with uni-element and by theorem 1 and definition A, a maximal set of B forms a Boolean ring .

Then by definition Therefore B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Theorem 1.5.

A Boolean-near-ring (B, \vee, \wedge) is having the proper subset A , associate ring is of the form $A = u_J$, where u is a non-zero of A and J is the set of idempotent elements of A , with suitable definitions for \vee and \wedge ,

$$a \vee b = a + b - 2a^0b = (a \cup b) - (a \cap b)$$

$$a \wedge b = a \cap b = a^0b = ab^0.$$

Then B is a Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

Proof.

Assume that the proper subset A of a Boolean-near-ring B is of the form $A = u_J$, where u is non-zero divisor of A and J is the set of idempotent elements of A .

Now to prove B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

It is enough to prove that A is a maximal set with uni-element.

(i) It is sufficient to show that the set uJ is a maximal set having u as its uni-element and

(ii) If b belongs to the maximal set determined by u , then b has the required form $b = eu$, for some $e \in J$

Proof of (i) It is seen that $ue \sim uf$ (ie) ue is compatible to uf with uni-element u , for all $e, f \in J$, since idempotent belongs to the center of A . Also, $ue < u$, since $ue \cdot u = u^2e = (ue)^2$

Proof of (ii) We know that A is an associate ring, the associated idempotent a^0 of a has the property:

if $a \sim b$ then $a^0b = ab^0 = b^0a = ba^0$

If $a \in A_u$ then since $a < u$ and $u^0 = 1$,

$$\text{we have } A = u^0a = au^0 = a^0u, \text{ for all } a^0 \in J$$

Hence A is a maximal set with uni-element of of B by suitable definition and by theorem 1 then we have A is a Boolean-ring.

Then by definition,

Hence B is Smarandache-Boolean-near-ring.

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